
Full Paper

TOWARDS AN ANALYTIC FRAMEWORK FOR TWITTER INFLUENCERS IN BOKO HARAM DISCOURSE

Victor E. Ekong

Department of Computer Science,
University of Uyo,
Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
victoreekong@uniuyo.edu.ng

Daniel E. Asuquo

Department of Computer Science,
University of Uyo,
Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
danielasuquo@uniuyo.edu.ng

Pius U. Ejodamen

Department of Computer Science,
University of Uyo,
Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
piusejodamen.phd.std@uniuyo.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Boko Haram is a deadly religious extremist group involved in acts of terrorism. Their operations in parts of West Africa for about a decade with no respite has triggered the need for an innovative approach to prevent further damage to the economies of affected countries. In this study, we focus on eliciting knowledge from discussions in Twitter about Boko Haram. Python programming language and Tweepy library were used to pull related tweets from Twitter, spanning seven days. The popular and top influencers discussing issues about Boko Haram based on their number of followers, their verified status, as well as the number of tweets liked by other users, are reported. The findings from this report will be a useful resource for security agencies battling Boko Haram and others affected by their operations. Available data show that news media are the most common verified Twitter influencers discussing issues of these terrorists. Notably, security agencies involved in the fight against the sect do not significantly engage with the public in Twitter. It was also shown that the number of followers is a vital metric in determining influencers. Future research may consider the use of all relevant features in determining Twitter influencers.

Keywords: Twitter Influencer, Followers, Boko Haram, Analytic Framework, Big Data

1. INTRODUCTION

Twitter is a microblogging platform suitable for interactions. Communication in the platform is achieved by posting messages called 'Tweets', which can be read by anyone. The first tweet was posted on the 21st of March 2006 by the creator of Twitter – Jack Dorsey. Since then, over 6,000 tweets are generated every second, around 350,000 per minute, and an estimated 500 million posts daily (Twitter Usage Statistics, 2021). This volume of data continuously generated by Twitter qualifies it as Big Data.

Twitter is one of the common social media sites used across diverse age groups, cultural backgrounds, political and religious affiliations. Twitter supports several linguistic communications including English, Arabic, and many others. Tweets can be in the form of pictures, videos, website links, or text – of not more than 140 characters. These tweets are 'cost-effective' means to diffuse information through influential users (Bakshy et al., 2011).

The social interactions between users can reflect influence (Cha et al., 2010). The action of one user can influence the action of another. For example, a popular user who posts about 'Boko Haram' can ignite the desire of his/her followers to make similar posts, retweet, like or reply to the post. Events that occur offline often trigger an online discussion.

Due to serious security challenges, it is not unusual to find most Twitter users discussing security matters. In West Africa, and Nigeria in particular, the activities of Boko Haram (BH) has attracted heated debates in Twitter. Issues of killings, bombings, kidnapping, rape, destruction of private and government properties, over-running state security apparatus, and open intimidation of government have been attributed to BH. Several attempts to quash or negotiate with them have proved abortive.

BH is a globally recognised extremist Islamist movement, whose ideology is based on the sectional Wahhabi theological system (Umar, 2013). In 2013, the United States of America and British governments designated BH as a terrorist organisation; while it was designated as an al-Qaeda affiliate in 2014 by the

United Nations (Campbell, 2014). BH is believed to be receiving varying levels of support from other jihadist organisations in Africa and beyond (Umar, 2013). Some other individuals are enticed by the teachings of radical charismatic clerics who assure them of relief from their acute poverty and lack of justice, when an Islamic state is enthroned (Campbell, 2014; Umar, 2013).

The success of BH can be largely attributed to the unchallenged propagation of its ideology. Counter-ideology war is critical in dealing with the BH menace. Umar (2013) noted that Nigeria, which is most affected by terrorism, has failed in this 'war of ideology' (p.57). Public enlightenment is recommended to be carried out using the media. Twitter is available to security agencies and stakeholders combating BH to embark on counter-ideology.

There are daily news reports about BH on Television, print and online media. Twitter generates volumes of information from which knowledge can be obtained to aid security measures in combating crime. This study aims at identifying those who influence discussions about BH in Twitter. We consider the accounts with most followers and those who actively discuss the issue. A sample dataset of BH related tweets are presented and influential users are reported based on how active they are on Twitter and their number of followers.

The obtained data is analysed to bring to the fore, some hidden knowledge about BH. Vital research questions to be addressed include: who are the top influencers discussing issues about BH? How genuine and reliable are the influential Twitter accounts? How many of their tweets are favourites? Who are the major stakeholders expected to be interested in BH discussions?

Information gathering is a cardinal requirement for effective security. Hence, this report presents an analytical framework projecting the major influencers discussing issues related to BH, which will be a very useful resource for security agencies, international organisations and other stakeholders with business interests in Nigeria. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a detailed

description of related works in Twitter user influence research. Section 3 discusses features of popular and influential Twitter users. Section 4 presents the proposed analytical framework for Twitter influence profiling. Section 5 presents the analysis of the results of experiments performed. Finally, the paper concludes in Section 6 with some recommendations.

2. RELATED WORKS

Several studies have analysed popular users in Twitter. While some were region-centric, others were domain-specific. A region-centric study of Twitter users living in Pakistan or interested in discourse related to the country was carried out by Khan *et al.* (2016). They crawled the Twitter space based on Pakistan's longitude/latitude and hashtags ("Pak" and "Pakistan"). The study found several data attributes useful in the analysis such as hashtags, user mentions, Universal Resource Locators (URLs), tweet text, and the Twitter ID. The number of followers was the main feature used to determine a user's influence. The research findings showed that the active users were not having more followers and vice versa. Whereas, Zheng *et al.* (2020) introduced a time-sensitive and topic-specific influence measurement method for rating Twitter influencers. They reported a high precision in detecting top influencers in domain-specific discourse.

Katarla and Rao (2017) analysed and predicted the popularity of hashtags on Twitter. The study was aimed at benefiting the media, advertising, and marking organizations who need information about users' interests. In the research, they created a prediction model to process real-time tweets, clean out unwanted text, and distinguish trending/non-trending topics. The number of followers who used hashtags in their posts was also analysed.

TwitterRank, which is an extension of the PageRank algorithm, was developed by Weng *et al.* (2010) to identify influential Twitter users. The influence was measured, taking into cognisance, the similarity of the topic and the link structure of the users. The study showed a strong relationship between the *followers* and the *followed*; users tend to also follow those that

are following them. TwitterRank measured the influence of Twitter users concerning the topic of discussion and analysed the concept 'homophily' – which has to do with 'following your follower'. Cha *et al.* (2010) discussed metrics for measuring influence in Twitter. They investigated the changes in the influence of users with changes in time and topic of discussion. In the study, they noted the role played by 'indegree' (the number of followers of a user), the retweets and mentions they have received. A major finding was that having a high score in one metric may not guarantee a high score in the other metrics. Furthermore, the authors noted that some users with high followers may not attract as many mentions and retweets of their posts. They proposed that more tweets on a topic are necessary since influence cannot be attained suddenly.

In related research, Bakshy *et al.*, (2011) emphasised the importance of influencers in the diffusion of information. Rather than use one metric in measuring influence, Bakshy *et al.* (2011) measured influence in Twitter for the whole diffusion tree for each event.

3. FEATURES OF POPULAR AND INFLUENTIAL TWITTER USERS

Twitter provides a region of cyberspace to reliably measure the level of influence some users have over others. Some features extensively used to determine Twitter influencers include the number of followers, re-tweets, unique mentions, and likes of their tweets (Khan *et al.*, 2016; Katarla and Rao, 2017). Also vital is the verification status of the user. Twitter provided the 'verified' status of an individual as proof that the user is what he/she claims to be. However, there still exist several influencers who are not verified.

3.1 Verified Account

A verified account is that which Twitter has acknowledged as being authentic. Hence, posts from such an account can be more reliable or attributable to the poster. Most verified accounts belong to well-known social influencers, politicians, entertainers, athletes, religious leaders, public affairs analysts,

journalists, and news outlets amongst others. A blue badge is displayed to indicate that the Twitter account is of public interest and is verified. The other type of account – regular account – is not validated by Twitter and has no blue badge. The regular account forms the majority of the public posts as observed by previous studies (Khan *et al.*, 2016). Information from the regular account should be consumed with caution as tweets from it may be fake, rumour, or simply unreliable. It is noteworthy that some popular individuals may not have their accounts verified. The reason for this is referred for future studies.

3.2 Following and Followers

A Twitter user whose posts are well received will attract other users. When a user chooses to follow updates of another user, it is referred to as ‘following’. Following a tweet is similar to subscribing to the tweets of the user being followed. A follower can also receive a direct message (DM) from the person. This type of relationship provides the opportunity to exercise some form of influence on other users. It means all the followers will have their timelines displaying any post by the influencing user, thereby increasing the reach of their tweets in the network. While positive and beneficial tweets can be posted, there is also the tendency to post propaganda to large followers in the network. However, a follower can simply ‘unfollow’ any account deemed offensive or undesirable without the person being notified.

In most cases, influential Twitter users also follow others in the network. They like, retweet, and reply to other posts too. The user whose updates is followed up is known as a ‘friend’ or ‘following’. To measure users’ social influence and associations, it is imperative to observe the number of their friends – both those they follow and those that follow them.

3.3 Likes and User Mentions

A user can express appreciation for a tweet by clicking on the ‘small heart’ icon (Twitter Usage Statistics, 2021). This feature is known as ‘Like’ in Twitter. Twitter ‘Like’ is a very important feature to measure the influence of a tweet and the account involved. A user who generates many likes for various posts can be

accepted to be tweeting contents of interest. Hence, this study considers the ‘likes’ received in examining the influence of a user.

User mentions in Twitter refer to a tweet that includes a user’s name preceded by an ‘@’ symbol; for example, @username. It enables tweets to address another account. Consequently, users are mentioned if it is believed they are interested parties or if their attention is deliberately being drawn to the post. On the Twitter ‘Notification tab’, the mentioned user is informed of the post for necessary action. Notably, mentions can only be visible to the public if the tweet of the sender is not protected.

3.4 Retweets and Replies

A reply is a post made in response to another Twitter user’s post. The replies are visible to the public except if the user’s tweets are protected – in such cases only followers can view the replies.

On the other hand, a retweet is the posting of another user’s post. The retweet feature makes it easier to share posts of interest. ‘RT’ is used at the beginning of retweeted posts to indicate that it is not an original tweet but another user’s content. It is, however, possible to add one’s comments before retweeting. Every retweet is a conscious activity since a user is prompted to read a tweet that had not been opened before retweeting. The essence of the prompt is to eliminate ignorant and erroneous retweeting. Thus a retweeted post is considered to be of interest.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Twitter data was pulled based on search criteria related to ‘Boko Haram’ using the Twitter application programming interface (API). To obtain data from Twitter, approved access must first be granted. Required access credentials include the customer key and token, as well as the access key and token secret. The architectural design for this research is presented in Figure 1.

Python programming language was used in this study. It is a widely used language with rich libraries for efficient program implementation. The most important library used is ‘Tweepy’ (Roesslein, 2021),

which is a wrapper for the Twitter API. It interfaces with the Twitter environment to enable developers to programmatically manipulate records through a registered account. The rules for using the API are well documented. Some other libraries used include Pandas and Comma Separated Values (CSV) which were used to create and manipulate data-frame.

4.1 Analytical Framework for ranking Twitter Influencers

Figure 1: Analytical Framework for ranking Twitter Influencers in BH Terrorism

Using the approved credentials, the Twitter platform was randomly crawled for English language tweets. The features relevant to this study were obtained and stored as a .csv file format, which serves as our dataset. Further analysis can be performed on the dataset, as indicated in Figure 1. Features extracted for

analysing the Twitter influencers discussing issues of BH: number of the user’s followers, number of friends, likes/favourites received, screen name and verification status of the account, Tweet identity (TweetID), date the tweet was posted, as well as the tweet text.

The dataset was pre-processed to eliminate noise and unwanted data. For instance, to qualify for use in the analysis, the number of followers must exceed 30 and the user must have posted more than 10 tweets. This is the same as the inclusion criteria used by other researchers (Weng et al., 2010; Cha et al, 2010). Also, the extracted data had varying values of some features (such as the number of likes/following/friends, etc.) with changes in time. This is because, during the crawling process, changes are being made to the account – more people are clicking buttons to like their posts or following the user. The most recently updated value is used for analysis while others for the same account/tweet are discarded.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Twitter Influencers Discussing Boko Haram

To determine the influential Twitter users, we rank them according to their number of followers. This is similar to several applications, including Twitter, that rate influence of users by the number of other users following them (Weng et al., 2010; Khan et al., 2016). In addition, we analyse how active the user engages with others in the social community by tweeting often. Active Twitter users contribute significantly to the overall contents on the network and re-echo some posts of others.

Table 1 shows the top 30 Twitter influencers involved in discussing issues related to BH. It is worthy of note that 18 of them have over 1million followers each.

Table 1: Twitter Influencers ordered by number of followers

S / N	User's Name	Number of Followers	Total Tweets Posted	Verified	User Details
1.	Channelstv	4678666	156242	TRUE	News Outlet
2.	MobilePunch	4216918	460638	TRUE	News Outlet
3.	SaharaReporter	3659176	132315	TRUE	News Outlet
4.	vanguardngrnews	3092133	597334	TRUE	News Outlet
5.	GuardianNigeria	2128507	227076	TRUE	News Outlet
6.	Lindaikemi	1887597	194969	FALSE	Celebrity blogger
7.	Nigeria Newsdesk	1828392	222606	TRUE	News Outlet
8.	daily_trust	1797658	551945	TRUE	News Outlet
9.	Gidi_Traffic	1702078	963984	TRUE	Business/Blogger
10.	PremiumTimesNG	1648257	296126	TRUE	News Outlet
11.	TheNationNews	1597852	262768	TRUE	News Outlet
12.	DeleModu	1580873	143457	TRUE	Politician/Celebrity blogger
13.	DailyPostNGR	1434191	474163	TRUE	News Outlet
14.	THISDAYLIVE	1407230	117002	FALSE	News Outlet

15.	HQNigeriaArmy	1343611	5506	TRUE	Nigeria Army
16.	CNNAfrica	1306558	11992	TRUE	News Outlet
17.	NigeriaInfoFM	1102550	215247	FALSE	News Outlet
18.	NTANewsNow	1054634	81025	TRUE	News Outlet
19.	LeadershipNGA	980106	418714	TRUE	News Outlet
20.	realFFK	974545	28017	TRUE	Politician
21.	Renomokri	905085	60076	TRUE	Politician
22.	GovAyofayose	895050	3144	TRUE	Politician
23.	LegitNGnews	829308	292112	TRUE	News Outlet
24.	SAMKLEF	797300	30946	TRUE	Business/Blogger
25.	Segalink	782729	404405	FALSE	Celebrity
26.	abati1990	709140	71142	TRUE	Politician
27.	yabaleftonline	702638	66954	TRUE	News Outlet
28.	thecableNG	694094	170293	TRUE	News Outlet
29.	pmnewsigeria	639234	307402	TRUE	News Outlet
30.	Naija_PR	634529	176619	TRUE	News Outlet

Table 1 indicates that the number of tweets posted does not guarantee an increase in the number of followers and vice versa. For instance, while 'segalink' with 404405 posts has 782729 followers, 'channelstv' with 156242 posts has 4678666 followers – which greatly outnumber the former. However, it is observed in Figure 2 that 'segalink' is among the top 10 users with the highest tweets, while 'channelstv' is 20th. Similarly, while 'Gidi_Traffic' has the highest number of tweets, its followers are significantly

outnumbered by those of ‘MobilePunch’. The same applies to many other Twitter users shown in Table 1. The reason for this behaviour is worthy of future research.

Notably, the Nigerian Army (‘HQNigerianArmy’), as expected, was listed among users with the highest number of followers. However, its posts are significantly lower than others in that category. This means it is not well engaged with the public on Twitter. Considering that the Nigerian Army is a major security force involved in combating BH, it is being followed by more people but has provided only 5506 tweets since the creation of their account in April 2013.

Figure 2: Top 10 Twitter influencers ranked by number of tweets and their followers

5.2 Analysis of verified Twitter Influencers

A verified account affirms that the account is a human and not a bot. It bestows some legitimacy on the user. Hence, tweets from a verified account can be considered genuine and reliable. Except for ‘lindaikaji’, other top 10 influencers had their accounts verified. We also report that most of the top-rated influencers discussing issues of BH are verified news outlets. Thus, information emanating from them need to be taken seriously by relevant security agencies and other interested persons/organisations. Similar to the report of Khan et. al. (2016), most of the downloaded tweets were from unverified accounts but the ranking Twitter influencers discussing BH were verified.

Furthermore, we manually stated the description of each user. Although news media dominated the influencers reported in Table 1, politicians, celebrities, and business interests also engaged in the discussions about BH. Among the security agencies involved in managing the BH menace, only the Nigerian Army (‘HQNigerianArmy’) ranked high among the verified accounts.

5.3 Analysis of users’ favourites to posts of Twitter Influencers

The favourite Twitter influencers are determined by the total number of their tweets liked by other users. It can be observed in Figure 3 that ‘segalink’ – a businessman, activist and media host – with an unverified account has received the most likes. This reveals that users seem to pay less attention to the verification status of the poster before deciding the posts to like. Again, news-based accounts are the favourites of Twitter users, except for few politicians. We suppose that users would rather ‘like’ any tweet they are favourably disposed to.

Figure 3: Number of likes received by the top influencers

5.4 Analysis of Twitter users mentioned in discussions on Boko Haram

The major stakeholders expected to be interested in BH discussions are mentioned in relevant tweets. This information is extracted by ranking all unique user

mentions found in tweets. Noting that a person known to be interested or associated with a topic will usually be mentioned to give the post a wider audience and to draw such person's attention to the discourse. Figure 4 shows that the news outlet '@saharareporters' had the highest (1112) user mentions. Following at the distant second place is the '@hqnigerianarmy' which is at the epicentre of the ground war with BH. In the third place is '@mbuhari' – the President and Commander-in-Chief of the Nigerian Armed Forces. Other users mostly mentioned in BH discussions in Twitter are mostly news outlets and politicians.

Figure 4: Top 10 Users mentioned in BH discourse

Twitter users often draw the attention of other users believed to be interested parties in the fight against BH. It can be noticed that user mentions cannot solely be used as a metric to determine a user's influence in Twitter.

6. CONCLUSION

Boko Haram is a topical issue of interest. Twitter is a social media platform that enables the citizenry to discuss issues of concern and react to other posts. With the increase of followers, users become popular and may exert some influence on others by their opinions. In this study, the number of followers was used to rank Twitter influencers discussing issues related to Boko Haram. The linguistic properties or meanings of their text was not considered but the active Twitter users with a high number of tweets,

followers, likes and user mentions were analysed. The Tweepy pre-processed data excluded irrelevant and noisy data and the result from the analysis indicates that '@Channelstv' has the highest number of followers, but the posts by '@segalink' attracted more likes. Also '@saharareporters', a verified news outlet, was mostly mentioned in tweets. It can be concluded that verified news media are the top influencers on BH related discourse. The data reveals that security agencies at the forefront of combating BH engage less with the public on Twitter. Security agencies can gain some intelligence if they engage more with online stakeholders in the fight against BH, through posting reliable information to counter falsehoods that may exist in cyberspace. Although politicians and celebrity bloggers made the list of top influencers, many are non-verifiable accounts; hence are not reckoned with as reliable sources of information in this study. The study further shows that various metrics produced different top-rated influencers. And the result obtained exhumes important information that can unravel the behaviour and feelings of social media users. Future studies improving this work shall explore data analytical techniques in determining Twitter influencers.

7. REFERENCES

- Bakshy, E. et al., 2011. 'Everyone's an influencer: Quantifying influence on twitter', *Proceedings of the 4th ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining, WSDM 2011*, pp. 65–74. doi: 10.1145/1935826.1935845.
- Campbell, J., 2014. 'Boko Haram : origins, challenges and responses'. *The Norwegian Peacebuilding Resource Centre*.
- Cha, M. et al., 2010. 'Measuring User Influence in Twitter: The Million Follower Fallacy', *Proceedings of the Fourth International AAAI Conference on Weblogs and Social Media*.
- Katarla, K. V. and Rao, V. V., 2017. 'Analyzing and Predicting Hash tags Popularity on Twitter', 15(11), pp. 9–16.
- Khan, R. et al., 2016. 'An Analysis of Twitter users of Pakistan'. Available at:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325396654_An_Analysis_of_Twitter_users_of_Pakistan
(Accessed: 24 April 2021).

Kharde, V. A. and Sonawane, S. S., 2016. 'Sentiment Analysis of Twitter Data: A Survey of Techniques', *International Journal of Computer Applications*. Available at: <http://ai.stanford>.

Twitter Usage Statistics, 2021. *Internet Live Stats*. Available at: <https://www.internetlivestats.com/twitter-statistics/>
(Accessed: 4 June 2021).

Umar, A. M., 2013. 'Nigeria and the Boko Haram sect :

adopting a better strategy for resolving the crisis'. *Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, California*. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10945/34755>.

Weng, J. et al., 2010. 'Twitterrank : Finding topic-sensitive influential Twitterers', *WSDM '10: Proceedings of the third ACM international conference on Web search and data mining*, pp. 261–270.

Zheng, C. et al., 2020. 'Measuring Time-Sensitive and Topic-Specific Influence in Social Networks With LSTM and Self-Attention', *IEEE Access*, 8, pp. 82481–82492. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2991683.